

The Relation between Proactive Coping and Well-Being: An Example of Middle-Aged and Older Learners from Taiwan

Authors : Ya-Hui Lee, Ching-Yi Lu, Hui-Chuan Wei

Abstract : The purpose of this research was to explore the relation between proactive coping and well-being of middle-aged adults. We conducted survey research that with t-test, one way ANOVA, Pearson correlation and stepwise multiple regression to analyze. This research drew on a sample of 395 participants from the senior learning centers of Taiwan. The results provided the following findings: 1. The participants from different residence areas associated significant difference with proactive coping, but not with well-being. 2. The participants' perceived of financial level associated significant difference with both proactive coping and well-being. 3. There was significant difference between participants' income and well-being. 4. The proactive coping was positively correlated with well-being. 5. From stepwise multiple regression analysis showed that two dimensions of proactive coping had positive predictability. Finally, these results of this study can be provided as references for designing older adult educational programs in Taiwan.

Keywords : middle-age and older adults, learners, proactive coping, well-being

Conference Title : ICHE 2014 : International Conference on Higher Education

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : June 26-27, 2014